

The new wheelchair symbol: enabling or disabling disability? A structuralist analysis on the plausibility of the new ISA.

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Abstract In 2012, a new International Symbol of Access (ISA) has been introduced by designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny as a counter-image to the ubiquitous wheelchair symbol of Karl Montan. By presenting a new symbol, the designers wanted to draw attention to some of the visual attributes of the former symbol they found problematic, such as its passive and robot-like depiction of a human being, while simultaneously addressing, in a broader sense, the place and the degree of acceptance of the disabled within society. Comparing the two sides of this 'design activism', that is creating a more clear and intelligible sign connoting disability and raising a social discussion concerning the disabled, will be the focus of the essay, assessing how the emotional-driven reasons for creating the new symbol might transcend its functionality as plausible 'ISO symbol'.

Keywords Disability, Sign and symbols, The International Symbol of Access (ISA), Connotation, Emotional design

Introduction

Logo's and signs. They are all around us and have become so integrated in every day's transactions all over the globe – pointing the way, indicating information, or showing access – that they appear to have become ubiquitous. Overall catheterized by being simple and straightforward, they are instantly recognized and consequently, according to N. Klein, 'Logos [and signs] have become the closest thing we have to an international language, recognized and understood in many more places than English' (as cited in Berman, 2013, p. 54). The International Symbol of Access (ISA), the wheelchair symbol designed by Karl Montan in 1969, is said to be one of the five most recognized signs in the world today (RI Global, n.d.) (Figure 1).

In the beginning of September 2014, an article was published in the Dutch newspaper *De Volkskrant* announcing that recently a new wheelchair symbol had been developed (Figure 2), aiming at replacing the previous International Symbol of Access (Schoorl, 2014). This act draws attention to the symbols as such. Comparing the two signs, the changes that have been made are quite noticeable. Even though the blue background has stayed intact, the white lines have clearly altered in some ways. The arm moving backward, the body bended forward, the upward leg and the diagonal cutting through the wheel: the new symbol depicts the disabled in a more active way. Interestingly, it is especially when the new sign is introduced that suddenly the stiff, passive and robot-like depiction of a human being in the former symbol comes to the fore: ubiquitousness (i.e. invisibility) moves to awareness (i.e. visibility).

Figure 1. Karl Montan, *The International Symbol of Access*, 1969

Figure 2. Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny, *The Accessible Icon Project*, 2012

This was in fact the intention of the new ISA. By creating a more 'active' sign, designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny wanted to draw attention to some of the visual attributes of the previous symbol they found problematic. Their aim was generating discussion on the ubiquitous International Symbol of Access and, in a broader sense, at addressing the problems surrounding the disabled, being a rather neglected, undervalued and misprized group of society (VanHemert, 2013). As honest and sincere as this project may be, a certain ambiguity can be highlighted. Paradoxically, the official website of the new ISA states: 'People with disabilities have a long history of being spoken for' (The Accessible Icon Project, n.d.). The question that comes to the fore then is how the new symbol differs from not doing precisely the same. Moreover, looking at the design from a purely visual angle, the representativeness or veracity of the sign shed a doubt insofar as it wields an unnatural,

disproportionate pose. In this way it can be argued that the symbol conveys in fact more about the non-disabled, wanting to provide a counter-image and addressing a problem, rather than truly providing a different, innovative way of portraying disablement. In order to assess this assumption and the nature of the symbol, the following research question has been formulated: *To what extent does the message of the new ISA transcend its functionality as plausible 'ISO symbol' and in what ways does the sign reflect upon the relation between the disabled and non-disabled?*

This question assumes that more can be deduced from an artefact than simply being studied as an object that serves a certain function. In the latter case, that would be the ISA connoting disability and accessibility: indicating where disabled people can park, enter, sit, etc. The former encompasses a premise that has been expressed by material culture studies: 'Scholars working in the field of material culture studies aim to analyse how these relations [what objects do for and to people] are one of the important ways in which culture - and the meanings upon which culture is based - are transmitted, received and produced' (Woodward, 2007, p. 14). Hence, this essay will adopt a *structuralist approach*. Structuralism focuses not so much on who produced the product but rather on what it may or can tell about the society it was produced in: the underlying structures of cultural convictions. Structuralism implies that people obey to certain social rules, without them being taught in a conscious way. The individual is shaped by sociological and psychological structures over which one does not have control (Jones, n.d.). As a result, it is also believed that values, ideas, attitudes and assumptions are embedded within objects: '[Objects] reflect, consciously or unconsciously, directly or indirectly, the beliefs of individuals who made, commissioned, purchased or used the object and by extension the larger society to which these people belonged' (Prown, 1982, pp. 1-2).

In order to be able to determine the 'nature' of the ISA, society and the social relationships at large have to be analysed. The article will start with identifying the problems surrounding the disabled in society, with special attention to the *social model of disability*, placing the designers' motivation of creating the new symbol into context. In addition, 'underlying structures' within Western culture will be pointed out: that is the binary way of thinking. Subsequently, the development of the symbol will be discussed, resulting in a visual analysis deconstructing the sign. This will be done from a rather semiotic approach, as: 'The methodology of material culture is also concerned with semiotics in its conviction that artifacts transmit signals which elucidate mental patterns of structures' (Prown, 1982, p. 6). At last, through these different observations the credibility of the symbol will be examined, resulting in a conclusion speculating its plausibility.

Identifying disability as social problem

According to a factsheet from the United Nations, around 15 per cent of the world's population, estimated 1 billion people, live with some sort of disability. This makes the disabled the world's largest

minority (United Nations Enable, n.d.). It has to be reckoned that the term disability is extremely diverse. Unlike either of the ISA depicts, only about one tenth of the disabled people are physically or mentally disabled and require a wheelchair (Abberley, 2007). Despite these vast numbers, the disabled seem to be far from accepted by or integrated in society. Research has shown that disabled people are more likely to live in poverty, to be unemployed and to face discrimination in the workplace (Smith, 2010). A 2004 United States survey found that in the developed world, only 35 per cent of the disabled working-age people are in fact working, compared to 78 per cent of those without disabilities. However, two-thirds of the unemployed people with disabilities said they would like to work but could not find any job (United Nations Enable, n.d.). Perhaps not without correlation, disabled people are more likely to suffer from depression.

Being disabled has largely been explained from a traditional, medical point of view, as T. Titchkosky (2007) has formulated: 'The processes through which readers and writers constitute the problem of disability as a medical one [...] (S part 1.). The *medical model of disability* holds a rather individualistic approach and says people are disabled by their impairments or differences. In this regard, impairment is defined as long-term limitation of a person's physical, mental or sensory function, an individual deficit ("The Social Model of Disability", 2014). However, Martyn Sibley (2010), disabled himself, remarks on his blog that an individual may have a medical condition or impairment, but that this person is in fact labelled as disabled through three different types of barriers that are constructed by society. These are physical barriers (Sibley: 'When a building has steps, my wheelchair cannot access it and I am therefore disabled'), attitudinal barriers (Sibley: 'When their attitude is around my needs being an additional difficulty, I am disabled') and organizational barriers (Sibley: 'If I apply for a job [...]. If an employer refused to make 'reasonable adjustments' I would be disabled'). What Sibley is trying to argue here is that disability is not so much a medical or individual phenomenon, as it is a social problem.

This idea can also be found within the academic spheres of disability studies. The (British) *social model of disability*, an upcoming tendency since the last few decades, claims that disability is caused by the way a society is organized, rather than by a person's impairment ("The Social Model of Disability", 2014). The social model emerged from the arguments of the Union of Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS). In 1975 they had stated:

In our view, it is society which disables physically impaired people. Disability is something imposed on top of our impairments, by the way we are unnecessarily isolated and excluded from full participation in society. Disabled people are therefore an oppressed group in society (as cited in Shakespeare, 2013, p. 215).

What this citation illustrates is the distinction

between disability (social exclusion) and impairment (physical limitation). Although the social model does not ignore the 'body' as such, the primary focus is on how societies treat individuals with disabilities and the consequences of that treatment. The attention is focused onto social oppression, segregation, cultural discourse and environmental barriers (Shakespeare, 2013).

One important factor within the social model of disability is the role of the media, defined in terms of mass communication. When the media talks about disabled people, S. E. Smith (2010) notices that this is often accompanied by sentences such as 'in spite of their disability', describing disability as something negative that must be 'overcome' in order to succeed. Titchkosky (2007) has argued the same: through the mass media, people become aware of disability defined in terms of inability, lack and loss. In this regard, disability is something that is 'written into texts' for mass consumption. Even when disability is being evaluated as 'not so bad' or 'not really different', it is already positioned as unwanted, undesirable, or at least unusual; states Titchkosky. Moreover, the existence of for instance disability-related charities reinforce the status of the disabled as objects of pity (Shakespeare 2013). All these different 'narratives' prevalent within society contribute to a restricted representation of the disabled, since they do not include the possibility of claiming disability as a desired status. With this in mind, Titchkosky (2007) refers to the process of meaning making: '[...] we are active participants in making up the meaning of people' (§ part 1). That is, disability is made meaningful by the ways it is said to be: disability as made by culture, a social creation. In this light, the social model of disability has provided a structural analysis of disabled people's social exclusion (F. Hasler, 1993 as cited in Shakespeare, 2013).

The binary western world

Logos, signs and symbols also function on the level of mass communication as they reach many people and transmit specific, structured information. Apart from the fact how being disabled is presented by the ISA, what will be analysed further on, the fact that a wheelchair symbol exists in general already reveals some information regarding the structure of Western society. According to Jacques Derrida, meaning in the West is mostly defined in terms of binary oppositions ("Derrida, Deconstruction", 1994). In this case, the presence of the symbol reinforces the (possible-made) distinction between disabled and non-disabled people. Moreover, Derrida argues that often, within each pair, one of the terms is viewed as being superior or the general case, while the other one is regarded as inferior and the specific case, as the following citation illustrates:

In a traditional philosophical opposition we have not a peaceful coexistence of a vis-à-vis, but rather with a violent hierarchy. One of the two terms governs the other (axiologically, logically, etc.), or has the upper hand. To deconstruct the opposition, first of all, is to overturn the hierarchy at a given moment (Derrida, 1981, p. 41).

Figure 3. The Accessible Icon Project's stickers applied on the ISA in the streets of Boston.

In light of this research, that would be the non-disabled people being superior and influential in regard to people with a disability. The social construction of being disabled then is fed by the presence of the symbol. For instance, it indicates that certain toilets are adopted for disabled people, whereas others are not. However, when the 'physical barriers' prevalent in regular toilets would be diminished, there would be no need for a symbol. In this example, being disabled would not exist.

The development of a new ISA

Eliminating the strong binary oppositions that rule Western society seems hardly possible. However, changing the relation between the two opposites would be more workable. In this light, designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny started to create a new wheelchair symbol. They were unsatisfied with the previous ISA, the widely known wheelchair symbol designed by Susanne Koefoed in 1968 and later on modified by Karl Montan, displayed in many public spaces around the globe (VanHemert, 2013). They regarded this symbol as depicting the disabled as passive, dependent people, therefore upholding the negative construction of being disabled prevalent within society.

In order to draw attention to some of these visual attributes they found problematic, such as the robot-like depiction of a human being, they started a street art campaign in 2009 called *The Accessible Icon Project*. A new wheelchair symbol was developed that would display the disabled in a more active way. By plastering their new symbol in front of the former ones, the transformations in signs were observable: an active figure against the old, static one underneath (Baker, 2011; VanHemert, 2013) (Figure 3). In this way, they wanted to generate discussion about the ubiquitous International Symbol of Access of Montan and, in a broader sense, at addressing the (social) problems and stigmatization surrounding the disabled in society (Schoorl, 2014; VanHemert, 2013). Just as the authors discussed above, Hendren and Glenny had identified being disabled as a social construction. The development of a new symbol then can be placed

within, or at least related to, the social/structuralist discourse within disability studies. However, instead of doing so via written, academic accounts, *The Accessible Icon Project* can be seen as an agent that visually tries to demonstrate that disability is mainly a social problem.

This intention to change cultural and emotional values can in a way be related to the *drench hypothesis*, as formulated by Bradley Greenberg in 1988. Whereas the hypothesis was formulated in regard to television programmes, this research will expand it further to encompass all visual expressions and portrayals. The drench hypothesis states that an unusual positive portrayal of a minority group member on television (in addition via other means of visual culture) can have beneficial effects on the viewer's attitudes and behaviour, even though the majority of portrayals of that group are stereotypical (Greenberg cited in Blaine, 2007). To put it into other words: a single visual expression can have a significant impact on viewer beliefs, perceptions, or expectations about a certain group. It would be able to cut through all of the built up negative stereotypes and stigmas in the media landscape and re-educate people, changing their attitudes towards, in this case, disability and disabled people (Sibley, 2010).

Whether this hypothesis proves itself valid or not, it seems to be precisely the new ISA's aim: changing a mentality, as Hendren has expressed in regard to *The Accessible Icon Project*: 'We knew that a mildly illegal act would actually be the angle by which we could raise the conversation that we wanted to raise, which was not really about the symbol's graphic qualities, as such. It was about how do we represent people in public ways and what does this sign, this symbol which is after all historically really profound in what it guarantees as political access, what does that mean to us now' (as cited in Chokshi, 2014).

Initially, this 'guerrilla art' was in fact the final product of *The Accessible Icon Project*. It had not been the intention of Hendren and Glenny to develop a completely new symbol replacing the old one. The art project had been created to identify a problem, producing a discussion, and raising awareness. However, as the public response was highly encouraging and enthusiastic, Hendren noticed that: 'The response that came [...] made us realize that what people were looking for was, in fact, a new icon' (as cited in VanHemert, 2013).

In order to develop a true, adoptable ISA, the symbol had to comply with the *ISO 7001*, a standard of *The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)*¹ that defines a set of pictograms and symbols for the purposes of public information. Apart from its depiction – a symbol that clearly displays a wheelchair and signifies accessibility – the sign has to comply with other specific rules, like the requirement of a 70% contrast between the figure and the background. Moreover, an adoptable ISA demands a completely flat representation. Three years after the start of the project in 2012, a new wheelchair symbol was created, embodying the qualities of activity

Figure 4. The adjustments made for an adoptable ISO symbol.

Hendren and Glenny initially set out to capture but also adhering strictly to the *ISO 7001* standard (VanHemert, 2013) (Figure 4).

A visual analysis of the ISA

Complying with the rules set out by the *ISO 7001* standard, the new ISA is depicted two-dimensionally, without any shadowing or lighting. It is a highly simplified and abstracted image. As for the requirement of contrast, the sign displays a dark, blue square filled with white lines. In contrast with the blue, plain background, the white parts in the centre of the image are evidently the most important aspect of the whole image. It is not striking then that in comparison to the previous ISA these lines have altered in certain ways.

In case of the new ISA, the white lines are divided into three parts: a circle (upper right), a semi-circle (lower left) and a middle part. Despite this division, the shapes clearly form a whole together: they are part of one image and should not be interpreted individually. The former ISA existed just of two parts, and the endings are rather angular compared to soft, round forms that can be found in the new symbol. This creates a more human and user-friendly look. From a semiotic perspective, these characteristics constitute the signifier: the form the sign takes. The concept it represents is the signified. In both cases, the sign represents a person sitting in a wheelchair signifying disability. However, the way disability is displayed – its *connotation*² – is rather different.

In the symbol of Montan, the two groups of white lines represent what is human and what is chair. Hendren and Glenny believed that, consequently, in this design, the wheelchair overshadows its passive passenger (Lazarte, 2013). In the new ISA, the person and the chair are united as one whole, rather than as two separate elements. This would indicate that the chair

- 1 The *International Organization for Standardization (ISO)* is a non-governmental membership organization that give world-class specifications for products, services and systems, to ensure quality, safety and efficiency, and are instrumental in facilitating international trade (The ISO, n.d.).
- 2 Elaborating on F. Saussure's distinction between *signifier* and *signified*, R. Barthes introduced the terms *denotation* and *connotation*, describing the relationship between the signifier and its signified. Whereas denotation is the definitional and literal meaning of a sign (the signified), connotation implies a 'second-order' signifying system. Connotation refers to the socio-cultural or personal associations that might be attached to a sign.

The Icon Graphic Elements

Head Position

1 Head is forward to indicate the forward motion of the person through space. Here the person is the "driver" or decision maker about her mobility.

Arm Angle

2 Arm is pointing backward to suggest the dynamic mobility of a chair user, regardless of whether or not she uses her arms. Depicting the body in motion represents the symbolically active status of navigating the world.

Wheel Cutouts

3 By including white angled knockouts the symbol presents the wheel as being in motion. These knockouts also work for creating stencils used in spray paint application of the icon. Having just one version of the logo keeps things more consistent and allows viewers to more clearly understand intended message.

Limb Rendition

4 The human depiction in this icon is consistent with other body representations found in the ISO 7001 - DOT Pictograms. Using a different portrayal of the human body would clash with these established and widely used icons and could lead to confusion.

Leg Position

5 The leg has been moved forward to allow for more space between it and the wheel which allows for better readability and cleaner application of icon as a stencil.

Figure 5. Explanation of the graphical characteristics of the new ISA by the Accessible Icon Project.

is not a burden to bury, but illustrates it is rather something that is part of many disabled people's life: 'the person is no longer imprisoned by the chair - the chair is merely the vehicle with which he or she gains access' (VanHemert, 2013). It aims at showing that the chair is part of the person rather than the other way around.

Furthermore, in the former symbol, the person is passively sitting in his chair with his arm by his side. This implies that, in order to move forward, someone would have to push him. The new symbol replaces this passiveness by activeness. The elbow pointing backwards, the knee pointing up, the body bending forwards and the diagonal line cutting through the wheel: all these aspects create a feeling of movement and dynamics. *The Accessible Icon Project* has

explained these characteristics in detail, as Figure 5 illustrates, in which one concept has a prominent position: mobility. The symbol is designed to convey the independence of the disabled, their being active people, wheeling themselves rather than passively sitting in their chair, waiting to be pushed.

A realistic symbol?

Despite this unquestionably genuine aspiration, when examining the new ISA from a structuralist/semiotic point of view, different observations come to the fore that challenge the applicability of the symbol. From a purely visual angle, it is a rather complex image to deconstruct. If for instance the head of the person depicted is omitted, then what is left is hardly recognizable as a human body. This is due to the fact that if the symbol would literally be translated to

reality, it would be an unnatural and disproportionate pose. The person would have given an enormous swing at the wheelchair's wheels, moving forward with high speed. In this way, the symbol resembles Paralympic participants. Racing athlete Kurt Fearnley during the 2000 Sydney Paralympics (Figure 6) for instance holds the same posture as the symbol. In order to move forward as fast as possible, his arms are swung backwards and his body and head are bended forwards. The question that comes to the fore then is whether this is best way to represent the less mobile group of society.

Barry Gray, chair of the ISO committee on graphical symbols, has argued that this over-activity might be problematic. His point is that the new ISA design has attractive features, but he does not believe it is altogether appropriate as an indicator of accessibility: '[...] the symbol has to work in static situations. Part of its job is to mark wheelchair spaces in public transportation or indicate refuge in emergency situations [...]. The symbol also marks accessible routes, like ramps and lifts, not designed for speeding. I fear that the proposed symbol could give a misleading impression' (as cited in Lazarte, 2013).

This seemingly contradiction that Gray touches upon – portraying a less mobile group extremely mobile – questions the incentive behind the formation of a new ISA. T. Shakespeare (2013) has argued that a symbol cannot only be studied for reflecting underlying structures of society, but also as a mediator, capable of creating dynamics. As an active agent of human activity (i.e. Hendren, Glenny & society at large), the symbol can be seen as trying to transform societal structures. It has an ideological aspect in that it wants to give a counter-image regarding disablement, redefining the position of two 'binaries'.

By depicting the disabled in an active way, it seems as if the non-disabled (in the embodiment of designers Hendren and Glenny) wanted to show, perhaps too eagerly, that they have acknowledged a problem surrounding the disabled. However, the (over) willingness to provide a counter-image results in the depiction of a disabled person that seems to be moving forward in an excessive way. Consequently, it can be argued that the symbol is the equivalent of sentences such as 'but I don't think of you as disabled'. P. Abberley has argued that such expressions deny a key aspect of a disabled person's identity in what is intended as a compliment (2007). The same can be said for the symbol: it states, almost in a shouting manner, that the disabled are in fact active people, making the sign itself become, rather, exaggerated. By overemphasizing this (over) mobility it ignores the very fact that should be acknowledged: that the disabled are in theory less mobile. In this light it can even be argued then that the new ISA has moved from one end, that is the symbol of Montan depicting the disabled as dull and dependent, to the other end of the scale: almost ridiculing the disabled as being overly active – neither of them hitting the nail right on the head.

Figure 6. Kurt Fearnley during the 2000 Sydney Paralympics.

Ironically then, it appears that the new ISA is not so much intended to 'guide' the disabled, but rather to 'lecture' the non-disabled. The symbol is in fact meant to be viewed by them. The disabled themselves would not need reminding or convincing that they are active, independent people. It is the non-disabled people who need to change their image regarding this minority group. In this way the concept of design activism strongly comes to the fore, reinforced by the fact that the project started out as a street art campaign using design to create a political debate. Instead of solving problems questions were posed (Hendren, 2015). It is particularly in this context that the 'sticking' of a new kind of wheelchair symbol on top of the former one is sound, as was done by *The Accessible Icon Project*. In light of raising awareness, especially this contrast to the previous ISA gives the new symbol its strength as visual agent of the social disability discourse. This could also account for why designers Hendren and Glenny have chosen to stick with a wheelchair symbol rather than trying to find a completely new image for disablement altogether, since, as has been stated before, only one tenth of the disabled is actually sitting in a chair. Moreover, the question that arises is when the symbol will be world widely adopted – its march has already started – whether or not the same ubiquitous effect will occur as was, according to Hendren and Glenny, the situation with the former symbol by Montan.

These different aspects seem to assert that the ideological message is indeed the most important part of the symbol in regard to its functionality. It is revealing enough that the Museum of Modern Art in New York has (already) included the new ISA in their permanent collection, 'alongside other culturally-relevant designs from the last few decades' (Heasley, 2014). The fact that the symbol has been labelled 'culturally-relevant', rather than 'cleverly-designed' for instance, confirms all the more the centre of gravity of the whole design.

Conclusion

In theory it can be argued that new ISA functions as proper, working ISO symbol. It obeys to the rules set out by the *ISO 7001* and signifies disability. Nonetheless, looking at the 'emotional' intentions and the context of creating this new symbol, that is the

former 'passive' symbol by Montan in combination with the recognition of disability as a social problem, certain comments have been proposed.

The *social model of disability* is based on the notion that disabled people are an oppressed minority group and disablement a collective experience. Disability is viewed as a problem located within society, and the way to reduce disability is to alter the social and physical environment (Shakespeare, 2013). Even though the following quote is not specifically related to the development of the new ISA, its resemblance with the symbol's aim is striking.

Historical and contemporary (re)presentations of disability and people with disabilities by the dominant, able-bodied culture have dehumanized people with disabilities and rejected their agency as producers of knowledge. As people with disabilities have come to critique and reject these other-made (re) presentations, *new forms of disability culture(s) have emerged that (re)claim bodily and emotional performance and assert people with disabilities as experts on their own lives.* (Society for the Study of Social Problems, n.d. [emphasis added])

Especially the last part of the citation seems to encompass the purpose of the new ISA. The creation of a more active, mobile symbol was aimed at transforming a mentality by presenting the disabled in a more desirable way, as the title of the article published in the Dutch newspaper *De Volkskrant* epitomizes: 'Disabled person is no longer pathetic on logo' (Gehandicapte is op logo niet zielig meer: Schoorl, 2014). However, it is precisely by having this component that the credibility of symbol is challenged. Although the public response towards the symbol that can be found on the Internet, both from disabled as non-disabled people, is highly enthusiastic (the demand for the creation of a true adoptable symbol of *The Accesible Icon Project* came from society after all), by wielding a structuralist approach, more 'information' could be deduced from the object of study, moving beyond purely praising it as connoting activeness, independence and self-control. Different observations have been made asserting that the message of the new ISA does seem to transcend its plausibility as valid ISO symbol.

The (over) willingness of the non-disabled to provide a counter-image to the previous Symbol of Access has resulted in the creation of a new wheelchair symbol (sticking to this dogma all the same) that displays the disabled in an overly active way. The wheelchair-user seems to be moving forward in an excessive way, therefore almost ridiculing rather than acknowledging the quintessence of disablement: being less mobile. In this way, new ISA appears to be first of all intended for the non-disabled as an educational tool, rather than to indicate access to the disabled population. As a result, one wonders if the disabled – regarded as a social construction - have really 'gained' something from the new situation. Revealing in this regard is the observation made by Stella Young (2014), an Australian comedian and disabled herself. In her show she talks about being disabled in Western society, explaining

that when she was younger she was considered for the 'achievement award'. However, as she pointed out: 'I wasn't doing anything that could be considered an achievement if you took disability out of the equation.' Consequently, she concluded that people with a disability are seen as 'objects of inspiration'. Ironically, their purpose is to inspire you, to motivate you, as non-disabled person. As a group, the disabled are objectified for the benefit of another group: the non-disabled people.

This observation seems to uncover the 'hidden structures' in the creation of the new ISA. It can be concluded that the new symbol says more about the intention of the non-disabled, that is sending a new message to society – to both the disabled (presenting 'being disabled' in a more desirable way) and to the non-disabled (changing a mentality: the disabled as objects of inspiration) – rather than having a clear and intelligible sign connoting disability, acknowledging a society full of differences yet equalitarian all the same. One group is still objectified – however in a different way – to benefit the other; that is to set at rest the conscience of the non-disabled.

Images

Figure 1. The Accessible Icon Project. (n.d.) *Home*. Retrieved from <http://www.accessibleicon.org/icon.html>.

Figure 2. The International Symbol of Access (2016, January 31). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Symbol_of_Access#mediaviewer/File:International_Symbol_of_Access.svg.

Figure 3. Mars, R. (2014, February 19). Does the international wheelchair symbol need a redesign? [Web blog post]. *Slate Design's Blog*. Retrieved from http://www.slate.com/blogs/the_eye/2014/02/19/does_the_international_symbol_of_access_need_a_redesign_roman_mars_99_percent.html.

Figure 4. CIVA. (2014, February 13). *Accessible Icon Project*. Retrieved from <http://civa.org/civablog/accessible-icon-project/>.

Figure 5. The Accessible Icon Project. (n.d.). *Icon*. Retrieved from <http://www.accessibleicon.org/icon.html>.

Figure 6. Athletics wheelchair racing Kurt Fearnley. (2016, January 28). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kurt_Fearnley.

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